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OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICAL THINKING THROUGH PLAYING VIDEO GAME MACHINARIUM

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Abstract

Based on the research, an important feature of why computer games are a way of learning that is engaging and effective for their users is the fact that games allow knowledge to be put into the context when it becomes necessary and important. Some studies also found out that computer games have the significant potential for the development of the components of mathematical thinking, such as logical, strategic, combinatorial, and probabilistic thinking, spatial ability, and quantitative reasoning. In our paper we described our research on the possibilities for the development of mathematical thinking through playing video game Machinarium, developed by Czech indie game developer Amanita Design. For the analysis of this game, we used a qualitative approach: a content analysis, which is considered a suitable tool for examining video games. Both authors analyzed each of the puzzle minigames included in the game and coded them using the elements of the mathematical thinking that we described in the paper and are based on previous works in this area. After the analysis authors made a review of their codes and agreed about the elements of the mathematical thinking involved in the puzzle minigames. As a result, we identified that the game Machinarium could help in the development of logical, strategical, combinatorial thinking, and spatial ability.

Keywords: mathematical thinking, video games, content analysis of games, informal learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to [1], the number of active video game players reached 2.69 billion in 2020. At the same time, this number has been growing by an average of 5.6% per year since 2015. The report [2] states that players aged 18-25 spent an average of 7.48 hours per week in 2020 playing video games.

According to the study [3]: “Large majorities of players say video games provide mental stimulation (80 percent) and relaxation (79 percent). Video games help to connect us, and 65 percent of players say they play with others online or in person. More than half of parents (55 percent) say they play games with their children, and 92 percent pay attention to the games their child plays.”

Players' view that video games provide mental stimulation is also in line with Prensky's claim [4]. Prensky points to the knowledge of neurobiology, thanks to which we know that the brain is valid and changes throughout life. However, he goes on to say, such changes require hard, focused work several hours a day, five days a week. He notes: “Several hours a day, five days a week, sharply focused attention – does that remind you of anything? Oh, yes – video games! That is exactly what kids have been doing ever since Pong arrived in 1974. They have been adjusting or programming their brains to the speed, interactivity, and other factors in the games, much as boomers' brains were programmed to accommodate television, and literate man's brains were reprogrammed to deal with the invention of written language and reading (where the brain had to be retrained to deal with things in a highly linear way.)”

Prensky also refers to Moore [5], according to which we have developed hypertext thinking through the use of computers. Such thinking is parallel, not sequential, which is at odds with the traditional way of teaching. According to Moore [5] even “Linear thought processes that dominate educational systems now can actually retard learning for brains developed through game and Web-surfing processes on the computer.”

Several educational professionals also agree that video games have well-mastered learning principles and that we can learn from them a lot about learning [6, 7, 8]. One of the reasons why they consider games to be an engaging and effective way of learning is that they allow problem-solving skills to be developed in a context where those skills are necessary and important. We know from everyday experience that learning out of context or learning information that a person does not need leads to a low level of understanding and remembering. “Good games never do this to players but find ways to

put information inside the worlds the players move through and make clear the meaning of such information and how it applies to that world” [8].

Divjak and Tomić [9] state that “By playing computer games pupils discover and develop their abilities and skills, gain experience, learn and create. Games develop imagination and creativity”.

Research has also found a relationship between playing video games and developing mathematical thinking. Study results [10] confirm that video games develop the ability to solve mathematical problems best of all leisure activities, based on the analyzed data from The Child Development Supplement from PSID (Panel Study of Income Dynamics – a long-term survey that measures the economic, social, and health factors of families in America).

The participants aged 3 to 18 recorded leisure activities during a long period starting in 2006, and every five years the researchers tested them with the Woodcock-Johnson test for cognitive abilities. The results are that playing video games increases scores on mathematical thinking by up to 9.3%, an effect comparable to the effect that this study attributes to participating in educational activities with the same purpose.

Posso [11] conducted a study based on the analysis of the results of the PISA measurement from 2012. The study was conducted with more than 12,000 students from Australia. Pupils who stated that they play online games almost every day gained significantly more points in mathematical literacy than the average. However, as the author of the study himself states, it is not clear from this result whether video games develop mathematical literacy or, conversely, students who are proficient in mathematics more often choose to play video games as a form of entertainment.

Meta-analysis of Uttal et al. [12] shows the relationship between playing video games and the development of spatial imagination, in particular playing video games improves the player's ability to think about objects in three dimensions.

As we have already presented, the aim of our article is to focus on individual puzzle minigames in the video game Machinarium in terms of their contribution to the development of mathematical thinking.

As stated, [13] “Mathematical thinking is considered as the use of mathematical techniques, concepts and processes to solve problems directly or indirectly [14]. Mathematical thinking is a dynamic process that makes it easier for us to understand complex structures by combining our ideas [15] The individual tries to solve problems throughout his life at school, at work and in daily life [16] and for this he needs mathematical thinking.”

Considering previous definitions, we see that mathematical thinking is a very complex concept. When the literature is examined, different researchers consider different components of mathematical thinking. For the purpose of our paper, we decided to consider the influence of the puzzle games on mathematical thinking focusing on its following components of our choice. These components we already used in our similar study [17]:

“Logical thinking. “Logical thinking is the rational cognitive process of reflecting objective reality actively with the help of concepts, judgments, reasoning, and other forms of thinking. The basic forms of logical thinking include concepts, judgments, and reasoning. Logical thinking ways mainly include induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, as well as from the abstract to the concrete and so on” [18]. Important part of logical thinking is logical reasoning ability. “This is the ability to construct and follow a step-by-step logical argument. It is fundamental to mathematics” [19].

Strategic thinking. “Strategic thinking involves the synthesis of information to identify problems, connections, and rules (patterns) that encourage intuitive, innovative and creative thinking” [20]. Strategic thinking is therefore also necessary in mathematics for problem solving [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24].

Combinatorial thinking. Rezaie and Gooya [25] see combinatorial thinking in four levels of understanding: 1) investigating some cases, how am I sure that I have counted all the cases, 2) systematically generating all cases, 3) changing the problem into another combinatorial problem, and 4) understanding combinatorial reasoning. Combinatorial thinking is an important part of solving mathematical problems, Graumann [26] investigated the importance of combinatorial thinking in solving problems within the geometry curriculum and stated that combinatorial thinking is an important part of mathematical thinking. Also, according [27] combinatorial thinking is a special aspect of mathematical thinking and combinatorics can lead to understanding the strengths and limitations of mathematics.

Probability thinking. Jones et al. [28] understand it as thinking within probabilistic situations. They describe them as situations with multiple possible outcomes, and these outcomes cannot be determined exactly, but it is possible to create a distribution of possible outcomes based on long-term observation. Important part of mathematical thinking is also probability reasoning. "Probabilistic reasoning implies reason under uncertainty. This reasoning takes in consideration two important components: the variability of the result and randomness. The result or outcome is not determined, it varies depending on the possible and favorable cases (theoretical probability) or the frequency (frequentist probability) or some evaluation criteria (subjective probability) and it is related to randomness" [29].

Quantitative reasoning. "Quantitative reasoning is the ability to represent quantitative information and act on the representations to come to conclusions not previously known about the quantities represented or about the relationships between them" [30]. Quantitative thinking is also an important part of thinking when solving mathematical problems.

Spatial ability. "We use spatial thinking to understand the location (position) and dimensions (such as length and size) of objects, and how different objects are related to each other. It is important to understand that spatial thinking is not just one skill, but a set of different skills" [31]. These skills include, as mentions [12] spatial visualization, which involves the ability to imagine and mentally transform spatial information, and spatial orientation, which involves the ability to imagine oneself or a configuration from different perspectives. Such skills are important for solving a lot of mathematical tasks.

2 METHODOLOGY

Our research is focused on the possibilities for the development of mathematical thinking through playing video game *Machinarium*. We build on our previous research, which we published in [17]. In it, we analyzed the opportunities for the development of mathematical thinking in four video games, one of which was *Machinarium*. In this research, we take a deeper look at *Machinarium* and focus more precisely on the analysis of individual minigames.

Machinarium is a video game developed by a small independent *game* development *studio* based in the Czech Republic. The authors present this game in words: "Machinarium is our first full-length adventure game in which players take on the role of a robot who has been exiled to the scrap heap. Players must use logic, collect important items, and solve environmental puzzles to get the robot back into the city of Machinarium so he can rescue his robot-girlfriend, save the head of the city, and defeat the bad guys from the Black Cap Brotherhood." [32]

In our research we use a qualitative approach because we did not want to verify the predetermined hypotheses, but we wanted to understand the researched phenomenon as much as possible and then describe accordingly [33]. We researched individual minigames through content analysis.

Content analysis [37] is a research strategy in which researchers read the content of a selected product in a way that leads us to the answers to their research questions. Content analysis was originally used to analyze text, but today it is also used for the analysis of non-textual materials (in the analysis of paintings, films, works of art, etc.). Schmierbach [34] and Malliet [35] claim that content analysis is also a suitable tool for examining video games.

But they emphasize, in such an analysis it is necessary to think about the specificity of the examined medium. In contrast to written text or film, the content of a specific video game often varies from player to player. The content depends on the individual gameplay. So, it also applies at the same time, the researcher who plays the video game is also a co-creator of the analyzed content. For that we (both authors) played the *Machinarium* game independently and independently analyzed the minigames we found in the game environment. We coded them using the elements of the mathematical thinking that we described in the paper and are based on previous works in this area. After the analysis we made a review of our codes and agreed about the elements of the mathematical thinking involved in the puzzle minigames.

3 RESULTS

Through content analysis of game *Machinarium*, we have identified elements of mathematical thinking in individual minigames found in this game. We understand these elements of thinking in the sense we state them in the introduction of the article. As a result, we identified that the game *Machinarium* could help in the development of logical, strategical, combinatorial thinking, and spatial ability.

Among the elements of mathematical thinking determined by us [17] we were not able to find probability thinking and quantitative reasoning in the minigames.

The findings covering all minigames are shown in Table 1. To give the reader a better idea of the individual minigames, we have added links to their descriptions on the fan page Machinarium fandom [36]. At the same time, we draw the names of individual minigames from this page.

Table 1. Elements of mathematical thinking in the minigames.

<i>Minigame</i>	<i>Logical thinking</i>	<i>Strategic thinking</i>	<i>Combinatorial thinking</i>	<i>Spatial ability</i>
Pipe Control Puzzle	X		X	X
Furnace Hoist Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Junction Box Puzzle	X		X	
Prison Door Code Puzzle	X			
Prison Safe Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Oil Dispenser Puzzle	X	X		X
Docks Hoist Puzzle	X	X		
Pub Gomoku Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Temple Clock Puzzle	X	X	X	
Electricity Pole Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Plumbing Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Wall Lift Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Angry Fan Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Glasshouse Control Box Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Glasshouse Door Puzzle	X			
Arcade Game 1 Puzzle	X			X
Arcade Game 2 Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Elevator Control Box Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Bomb Timer Puzzle	X			X
Castle Safe Puzzle	X	X	X	X
Game in the Brain Puzzle	X	X		X
Dome Security Puzzle	X	X	X	
Spiders Puzzle	X	X		X

In the following text, we present a more detailed description of selected minigames with the results of the analysis of the components of mathematical thinking, which, according to the authors, they develop.

3.1 Pipe Control Puzzle

Figure 1. Screenshot from authors' gameplay.

This minigame is located in a closed room, and we activate it so that the robot touches the control panel located at the bottom right of the room. To do this, the robot needs to shrink.

The goal of this minigame is to move the oven on the ceiling so that we can move around it. We move the oven by entering a pair of numbers and letters, which we enter using two dials on the control panel. One dial contains the numbers 1-5, the other the letters A-E. By trying these dials, we find that one of them moves the tube horizontally and the other vertically.

The game develops logical thinking through the need to form judgments about the actual activation of the minigame and an awareness of the relationship between the dials and the movement of the oven, as well as the movement of the oven itself at different diaphragm settings. In exploring different pairs of numbers and letters and finding the right combination, the minigame also develops combinatorial thinking. Since we need to consider the positions of the oven in space when handling the oven, the game also develops spatial abilities.

3.2 Electricity Pole Puzzle

Figure 2. Screenshot from authors' gameplay.

This minigame is located on the bridge, it is activated after opening the door at the bottom of the lamp. We will see a panel with a sliding tiles puzzle, from which we need to create the pathway for the electrical circuit, leading between two red wires.

The minigame develops logical thinking in several aspects. The first time we touch the panel, one tile of the puzzle falls out and an owl steals it from us. The player must analyze the situation to figure out how to get this piece back. Logical thinking is also developed by appropriate judgments about the movement of individual parts. This movement also develops a spatial imagination, as the player needs to imagine the final position of the individual parts in order to get the desired end result by manipulation and must also realize what will cause the movement of the individual parts. The game also develops combinatorial thinking by the need to combine the movements of individual parts and strategic thinking by the need to plan moves and choose the appropriate strategy throughout the minigame solution.

3.3 Arcade Game 2 Puzzle

Figure 3. Screenshot from authors' gameplay.

The minigame is located in the game room and is activated when the second arcade machine starts. To start it, the robot must set the generator appropriately and generate electricity by cycling. This minigame consists of several levels, in each of which it is necessary to place a smaller red unit into a larger one in order to open the yellow door and we can get the blue square out. We can move the shapes using the blue square by pushing it on the sides of the shape. Levels have increasing difficulty.

Logical thinking needs to be used before the very launch of this minigame, where we need to figure out that we need to set up a generator and use a bike and find a suitable setting for this generator and how to use the bike. The player further develops logical thinking by getting acquainted with the principles of the game and revealing its rules (inductive thinking) and their subsequent use (deductive thinking). The game develops strategic thinking when planning individual moves and finding a suitable strategy to achieve a goal. The game develops combinatorial thinking in search of a suitable combination of moves. Since we manipulate the positions of planar objects during the game, the game also develops spatial abilities.

3.4 Bomb Timer Puzzle

Figure 4. Screenshot from authors' gameplay.

This puzzle is located on the top of the bomb placed on the tower. To activate the puzzle robot needs to access the bomb through the hole hanging from the toilet roll paper. The task is to deactivate the bomb before the timing device starts the explosion. We can see the code to do it written on the access door. The player needs to take out five fuses and order them in the correct order. To do this he needs to find correct paths of the five wires (numbered 1-5) and place fuses with the correct letter according to the code.

The player develops logical thinking by realizing that the sign on the door is the code to deactivate the bomb and also understanding the relationship between this code and the parts of the bomb. When searching for the path of individual wires, the player develops a spatial imagination.

3.5 Game in the Brain Puzzle

Figure 5. Screenshot from authors' gameplay.

This minigame is located in the head of the Mayor of Machinarium in his office. We can access it by connecting to the mayor's head with an electrical cable. The minigame is a maze puzzle. We need to get a gold key, which is used to open the room with the gun. Then we need to use this gun to kill all red enemy monsters.

The player develops logical thinking even before entering the minigame, when he needs to figure out that he will use the previously obtained cable. He further develops logical thinking in the analysis of the game itself, where he needs to find out that his task is to get a weapon and kill enemy monsters. Strategic thinking develops when planning the movement in the maze and the steps that the player performs during this movement (healing, hiding, fighting). Spatial imagination develops during the very movement and orientation in the maze, while at the moment we see only a certain part of the labyrinth and we must imagine its continuation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In our article, we analyzed the individual mihi games of the video game Machinarium developed by Czech indie game developer Amanita Design. For the analysis of this game, we used a content analysis. We focused on the elements of mathematical thinking. We think that the minigames included in the game Machinarium comprehensively develop the aspects of mathematical thinking mentioned in Table 1, namely the development of logical, strategic, combinatorial thinking, and spatial ability, and therefore we recommend playing it in order to develop them.

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